

MIRZO ULUG'BEK NOMIDAGI
O'ZBEKISTON MILLIY UNIVERSITETI
JIZZAX FILIALI

**KOMPYUTER ILMLARI VA
MUHANDISLIK TEXNOLOGIYALARI**

**XALQARO ILMIY-TEXNIK
ANJUMAN MATERIALLARI**

**TO'PLAMI
2-QISM**

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**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI**

**MIRZO ULUG‘BEK NOMIDAGI O‘ZBEKISTON MILLIY
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улучшает лингвистическую компетенцию. Используя язык, можно повышать интерес к изучаемому предмету и улучшать отношение к нему. Учитель предоставляет возможность изучать контент с разных точек зрения, что привлекает учащихся. CLIL позволяет учащимся больше контактировать с изучаемым языком, это не требует внеурочных часов и дополняет другие предметы. Одним из главных преимуществ CLIL является то, что данная технология позволяет разнообразить методы и формы аудиторной практики, повышает мотивацию и уверенность учащихся, дает учителям чувство профессионального удовлетворения.

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TEACHING ENGLISH PRONUNCIATION BY USING “PROJECT BASED LEARNING (PBL)” METHOD IN ENGLISH CLASSES

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Annotation. This study explores the teaching of English pronunciation in classes through the use of interactive methods, with a particular emphasis on applying Project-Based Learning (PBL) in group work. The research was organized into six main stages: preliminary preparation, planning, implementation, observation, reflection, and evaluation of results. Pronunciation, as a core component of English as a Foreign Language (EFL), is essential for developing effective oral communication. By improving their pronunciation, learners strengthen their ability to share ideas and opinions with clarity and confidence. Since pronunciation is a productive oral skill and the most common medium of verbal communication, its mastery is considered a crucial aspect of foreign language learning. The study highlights that PBL, as an interactive

method, makes pronunciation lessons more engaging, effective, and meaningful in English classes.

Key words: English pronunciation, Project-Based Learning (PBL), interactive methods, EFL, communication skills, group work, foreign language learning.

Statement of Intent. Classroom observations and teaching experience show that many learners face difficulties in mastering English pronunciation. One major issue is that insufficient time is devoted to pronunciation practice, as teachers often prioritize grammar, vocabulary, reading, or writing skills. Another contributing factor is learners' limited vocabulary, which restricts their ability to practice pronunciation effectively. Moreover, pronunciation instruction is frequently neglected by many instructors, despite its importance for language acquisition. At the primary school level, especially, pupils often begin to mispronounce words or hesitate in word choice, which negatively affects their communication skills. This research was therefore chosen to help learners improve their English pronunciation through focused practice and interactive methods.

Many pupils also experience anxiety about mispronouncing words, which leads them to substitute words and unintentionally change or confuse the meaning of their sentences. By learning to recognize sound production—for example, by feeling the throat vibrations when pronouncing certain sounds—students can monitor their own accuracy. Developing correct pronunciation habits can build confidence, reduce anxiety, and enable learners to speak English more fluently and effectively.

PBL in English Classes

According to Beckett [2002], in the context of foreign language education, PBL has a variety of terms that he finds interchangeable, such as project work, project method, project approach, project-oriented approach or project-based instruction. He claims that this method was firstly applied in foreign language setting more than 20 years ago in order to provide learners with chances “to interact and communicate with each other and with native speakers of the target language in authentic context” [2002, p. 54].

Beckett also argues that in comparison with general education there are seldom researches on PBL in foreign language education. And moreover, he alerts that in contrast to teachers from general education, foreign language teachers evaluate PBL process with mixed feelings. It emerges that implementing PBL in foreign language education shows increased tension in learners. Beckett points out that although the teachers were positively evaluating this method due to effective integration of subject-matter content, language skills as well as social and cognitive skills; some learners were expressing dilemmas and frustrations [2002]. Beckett views this state from cultural, philosophical and linguistic perspectives with one major recommendation to foreign language teachers. He acknowledges that though PBL has a deep potential for teaching and learning functional language, teachers must show the potential benefits also to learners through an accepted systematic framework that enables learners to see the possibilities of learning the language through this method. Otherwise, learners may more desire teacher-centered learning approach with traditional learning from textbooks, which for learners may represent the real work of learning English. In the

event of this fact, a systematic framework will be introduced in the later part of this work.

However, one should also mention the possibly challenging issues that PBL brings along in the area of language teaching. To begin with, most teachers are afraid of learners pronouncing their mother tongue instead of using English. In such case, Hutchinson acknowledges that this is very probably to happen mainly during the teamwork, nevertheless, he advises not to considerate it as a drawback but as a natural phenomenon about which there is no need to worry as long as the final product is in English, learners are provided with useful translation activities from various source materials and they have the opportunities to practice productive skills in English. Then, some teachers express their concerns about the loss of their firm control over the weaker learners so that they would be not able to cope with the work. This again might happen, yet, with the right teacher's attitude, solid regular class preparation and the responsible working and social environment, those learners are not neglected but either incorporated into co-cooperative learning groups or dealt with independently by the teacher, who, in his role of facilitator, is able to devote them more time. The last main concern is associated with correcting learners' language and with the number of language mistakes they are to make during the process.

This problem deals with the areas of language accuracy versus fluency and their potential balance. On the one hand, teachers should recognize which stages of PBL are more crucial to the need of accuracy practice and which stages are to produce language which is both accurate and fluent (Haines, 1989). Haines reminds that one of the main aims of PBL is to build learners' confidence and over-correction of teachers is likely to doom this goal.

To resume the role of PBL in English acquisition, it emerges that if PBL is carried out with a careful preparation, right teacher's attitude and decent knowledge, it comprises not only the general benefits that has been described in the first part of this work but also it produces further advantages. With respect to the English language, PBL affords learners to practice the target language they have consider needful, in real and meaningful situations. They are to express their own language needs along with creation of their own chosen end product; hence, it reinforces the learning of both language and the concrete content of PBL.

In reviewing the various studies done with PBL and PBL, it must be kept in mind that different researchers use the terms project-based learning and project-based language learning with different standards. Some educators have used all components of the gold standard PBL, while others only incorporate some or do not mention them in their studies, which cause variation in research results.

One of the most common benefits listed by both PBL and PBL advocates is increased motivation among the learners. One study of fifteen 11-12 year old learners in an elementary school in Greece found that the learners' intrinsic motivation seemed to increase, even among the lower achieving learners [Fragaulis, 2007]. These English as-a-Foreign-Language learners were guided to create projects having to do with their local history. They were divided into learning groups based on student interest and did their research and communication in the L2. The learners were given group roles to aid in carrying out certain tasks and to also aid the teachers in the learners' formative

assessments during the six-month project development. The author added that the learners “were more eager to experiment with the new language since they were less concerned with sounding silly” [p. 116]. The eagerness of the learners to participate in the project despite their imperfect English shows the power that PBL can have in student learning and engagement.

In an additional study of 38 high school learners, researchers wanted to find out what their learners thought about a PBL teaching approach [Tuncay & Ekizoglu, 2010]. Of the total learners, 19 used a PBL approach for a web design project (the experimental group), while the other class of 19 learners used what the teachers termed a teacher-centered approach and were used as the control group. Both groups were given instruction in web design and were given the assignment to create web projects. The experimental group was instructed to form groups based on interests and perceived talents. They were also allowed freedom to choose their projects rather than being dictated what to do by the teacher.

Conclusion. In summary, the review of literature and classroom-based studies indicates that Project-Based Learning (PBL) holds considerable potential for improving foreign language acquisition, particularly in fostering communication, motivation, and learner autonomy. While scholars such as Beckett [2002] highlight the limited research and mixed reactions of language teachers towards PBL, findings show that when applied within a systematic framework, this approach successfully integrates subject content, language skills, and social development.

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BO‘LAJAK PEDAGOGLARDA PEDAGOGIK QOBILİYATLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA YUZAGA KELADIGAN MUAMMOLARNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada pedagogik qobiliyatlarni shakllantirish jarayoni, bu jarayonda bir qator muammolar yuzaga kelishi, bu muammolar kadrlar tayyorlash